

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACH (CLT) IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS FROM TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS

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Abstract:

The current study mainly aims at investigating the effectiveness of using Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach in developing students' speaking skills at Sudanese secondary school levels from English language teachers' perceptions. Also, the study seeks to find out the problems that hinder the teachers' from implementing the CLT approach. To meet these aims and objectives the researcher employed a quantitative approach using a descriptive design. The researcher used the survey to collect data from the participants of the study. The random sampling technique was applied to select the sample out of all English language teachers at Omdurman Locality. Therefore, (100) female and male teachers have participated in this study. The information gained from the surveys was analyzed using the software Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study revealed the following findings: First of all, the majority of participants strongly agree that there is a positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective usage of the communicative approach. The main statements that gathered the highest level of response are: I think using CLT in my classroom helps my whole teaching process and using CLT in my class helps me share ideas and opinions with my learners. This means that most of the study participants assured that the use of CLT in the classrooms helped them to share the knowledge and facilitated their teaching process. Secondly, the majority of participants agree that there are effective factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach to develop students speaking skills. The main statements which gathered their highest level of response are the following: Lack

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of authentic materials hinder the use of CLA in my and classroom size makes using CLT in my classroom more difficult. This clearly shows that the most effective factors that hinder teachers from implementing CLT in their classes are lacking of authentic material and classroom size. Finally, the majority of participants strongly agree that the communicative approach to develop students speaking skills – in general, and the main statements which gathered their highest level of response: Using CLA enhances students speaking skills, and I think using CLT motivates my student to speak accurately inside and outside the classroom. This result indicates that their participants of the study confirmed that using CLT in classroom enhanced their students speaking skill and motivated them to speak fluently.

Keywords: communicative language teaching (CLT), speaking skills

1. Introduction

Although English is considered to be a critical language in Sudan and taught as an essential subject at both primary and secondary levels, it still counted as a significant problem for learners to master. For years, teachers have been changing and adopting various pedagogical approaches to encourage students to understand and use English as a conversation medium in their education and professions later on. The Sudanese government has also put a lot of works in performing pedagogical changes in the education plan to achieve its purpose in improving the use of information communication and technology (ICT) in the educational system. Many English language teachers have recognized several parts that guide students' concerns. McCrosky (1990) identified a phenomenon is known as communication apprehension (CA) to be a primary element associated with poor speaking skills when an *"individual level of anxiety or fear connected with either real or expected interaction with another person or persons"*. Students also revealed mixed feelings of anxiety, hesitation, shyness, unwillingness, etc. when it comes to talking or speaking in English. Nevertheless, since teaching and learning rely massively on communication, students must improve their communication skills.

At present, speaking a foreign language serves one of the essential requirements of today's society. Besides other skills and experience, it is regarded as one of the most influencing factors while appealing for a job or sustaining a particular work position under the condition of advancing the language level. Knowing a foreign language is a requirement for everyone in general. Consequently, the researcher considers the communicative activities a useful tool for English teachers to improve students' communicative skills. English learners no longer expect the traditional approach of their teachers based on developing mainly the grammatical competence and using methodology accessible in the past. Today, many educators expected teachers to provide their students with useful active knowledge of the foreign language, not just theory about the language.

The communicative approach focuses on a balance between fluency and accuracy and is the most suitable for those students whose aim is to gain confidence in speaking and conversational abilities. Nevertheless, speaking in a foreign language has often been seen as the most difficult of the four skills. *"While listening and reading involve the ability to receive messages correctly and are therefore referred to as receptive skills, speaking and writing, on the other hand, involve language production and are referred to as productive skills."* (Harmer 2015, P.16)

When students learn a foreign language, they very often accumulate a lot of knowledge (grammatical rules, lists of vocabulary items). Still, then they find out that they cannot use this language to communicate when they want to. Scrivener (2005, p. 147) claims that there seem to be some difficulties in moving the tongue from passive knowledge into active usage. Without experience in using the language, learners may tend to be nervous about trying to say things. Partly they may fear to seem foolish in front of others; they may worry about getting things wrong they may want to avoid teacher's comments or correction, and so on. It takes quite a long time for some students to express themselves, which leads to long embarrassing pauses while learners are trying to find out how to say what they want to say. Thus, the researcher intended to assess the impact of applying the (C.L.A) and evaluate the effects due to this approach in the target group speaking skills.

1.1 Statement of the Research Problem

Although Sudanese English language teachers, as other teachers, understood the importance of the communicative approach in developing the student speaking skills in the English language, some of them ignoring this approach in their teaching process. Consequently, the researcher would like to assess the effectiveness of using CLT in developing students' speaking skills. From her experience in teaching for many years, the researcher observed that secondary school students speaking abilities are not as required or they don't have high speaking abilities, which enable them to speak fluently and accurately. Therefore, the researcher hypothesized the cause of the problem due to the absence of CLT in their learning process. The research derived from the following questions: What is the impact of using CLT on the student's speaking skills. What are the barriers that hinder secondary school teachers from implementing the communicative approach in their teaching practice?

1.2 Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

- 1) To find out the relationship between teachers' attitudes and practical usage of the communicative approach.
- 2) To identify factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach do develop students speaking skills
- 3) To highlights the importance of CLT among English language teachers at the secondary school level.

1.3 Research Questions

- 1) What is the relationship between teachers' attitudes and practical usage of the communicative approach?
- 2) What are the effective factors that hinder teachers from using the communicative approach do develop students speaking skills?
- 3) To what extent does the communicative approach develop students speaking skills?

2. Literature Review and Previous Studies

2.1 The Definition of Communicative Language Approach (CLT)

(Richards, 2006) defined communicative language teaching as a set of principles about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn a language, the kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom. To date, there exists no absolute consensus regarding the meaning of CLT. Still, several authors believed that it is an approach that advocates the use of language as a means of communication. CLT is introduced and characterized in various ways in the literature (Harmer, 2015).

Richards and Schmidt (2013, p.99) stated that a communicative language approach is an approach to foreign or second language teaching. It emphasizes that the goal of language learning is communicative competence, which seeks to make meaningful communication and language use a focus of all classroom activities. Thus, the primary purpose of CLT is to develop learners' communicative ability, which helps them to interact effectively using a foreign language (Halliday, 1975).

Despite the variety of definitions that are attached to CLT, all the interpretations based on the following general assumptions or characteristics: The primary purpose of learning a language is to achieve meaningful communication through involving learners in an active process of target language interaction (Brown 2014, Canale and Swain 1980, Hymes 1972). The development of both accuracy and fluency required in learning the language. According to (Littlewood 1985, P.1), "*CLT gives planned emphasis on the functional as well as structural features of the language.*" Additionally, the building of communicative ability achieved by adopting a tolerant attitude towards errors. (Richards and Schmidt, 2013) argues that CLT is a learner-centered approach, where learners play a prominent role by spending the majority of the class time practicing the language (Richards and Rodgers 2001) while the teachers' purpose is to facilitate and monitor the teaching. (Nuna, 1991, p.1) said that the introduction of authentic texts into the learning situation expected in CLT. Although the above characteristics seek to achieve communicative competence, they differ in how this communicative competence to attained. In this vein, different researchers have made a clear distinction between the weak and secure versions of CLT (Ellis and Shintani 2014). (Howatt, 1984) differentiates between strong and weak versions in that the former one associated with the combination of structural features of a language and communicative elements. That means it aims to

use a traditional accuracy-oriented methodology to teach the characteristics of communication. (Holliday, 1994, p.170) points out that *"teachers who used to the lesson structure of the presentation, practice and production in the earlier "structural approach" find this version easier to understand and adopt than the more mysterious secure version."*

The weak version focuses on the practical and social side of communicative competence (Ellis and Shintyan 2014). Whereas the strong version emphasizes fluency-oriented method in reaching the communicative use of language and encourages learners to use language for communication rather than to practice the language in a controlled manner. (Ellis and Shintyan, 2014, p. 54) explained, *"the strong version is predicated on the principle that classroom language learning will proceed more efficiently if it occurs in a similar way to "natural" language learning."* However, in a context where English is regarded as a foreign language, it seems hard to learn or develop a style naturally during the interaction or use because of the lack of exposure to English in an environment of that context. In the context of this research, the weak version of CLT may be the most suitable version in which both structural and communicative elements have a role to play in EFL in the Sudanese Secondary school classroom setting for two reasons. Firstly, fundamental and traditional practices rooted in the Sudanese context for decades, and its influence is still evident in learning and teaching English. Many studies revealed, the use of conventional methods such as the Grammar-translation method, Audio-lingual method, and direct method is still in effect in Sudanese classrooms. Thus, it may be possible to argue that the use of the weak version of CLT, combining both the structural and communicative elements, will be appropriate to implement as well as being easier for teachers to adopt. Secondly, for a setting such as Sudanese where English is a foreign language, an understanding of language as Grammar and structure will help in developing and achieving communicative proficiency. This grammatical or linguistic knowledge can provide a foundation before further development of communicative competence. From the above distinction between the weak and robust version of CLT, and as a result of my research, I argued that the weak version seems to be more suitable to adopt in Sudanese secondary schools. It is essential to retrace the development stages of second language learning about the following language learning theories to understand the historical background of CLT.

2.2 The Goals of Language Teaching

According to (Jack (2006), communicative language teaching sets as its goal the teaching of communicative competence. First, grammatical competence refers to the knowledge we have of a language that accounts for our ability to produce sentences in a word. It relates to the understanding of the building blocks of sentences (e.g., parts of speech, tenses, phrases, clauses, sentence patterns) and how learners formed the sentences. Grammatical competence is the focus of many grammar practice books, which typically present a rule of grammar on one page, and provide exercises to practice using the grammatical rules on the other page. The unit of analysis and practice is typically the sentence. Grammatical competence is an essential dimension of language learning.

However, it is not involved in learning a language since one can master the rules of sentence formation in a language and still not be very successful at being able to use the word for meaningful communication. It is the latter capacity that is understood by the term communicative competence. Communicative competence includes the following aspects of language knowledge. For example, it was knowing how to use language for a range of different purposes and functions. Also, it includes Knowing how to vary our use of communication according to the setting and the participants. (e.g., knowing when to use formal and informal speech or when to use language appropriately for written as opposed to spoken communication) Knowing how to produce and understand different types of texts (e.g., narratives, reports, interviews, conversations) Knowing how to maintain contact despite having limitations in one's language knowledge (e.g., through using different kinds of communication strategies).

2.3 Classroom Activities for CLT

In CLT, classroom activities should be conducive to developing learners' communicative competence. (Littlewood, 1985) has divided the events into "*pre communicative activities*" and "*communicative activities*" (p. 86). He has asserted that classroom activities in CLT start with pre-communicative activities and finish with communicative activities. According to him, pre-communicative activities include different types of drills or question and answer practice. (Littlewood, 1985, p. 86) states that "*pre-communicative knowledge and skills can help the learner to communicate for meaning in communicative activities such as cued dialogues, role play, discussion, debate.*"

According to (Richards 2006), a significant feature of communication in CLT is the concept of the "*information gap*" (p. 18), this indicates the phenomena as in real communication; people usually interact with each other to receive the information they do not have. In CLT, "*pair and group work*" is emphasized because most of the activities are designed by teachers to carried out in "*pairs or small groups*" (Richards, 2006, p. 20). Through pair and group work, learners can learn to hear the language used by other participants of the group and get the chance to generate a higher amount of communication. Moreover, pair and group work have the potential to increase learners' motivational levels.

Unlike the traditional teaching methods, such as GTM, which adopted traditional techniques related to translation, rote learning, and grammar, the main characteristic of CLT, as indicated by (Larsen-Freeman, 1986), is "*almost everything that done with communicative intent.*" Communicative activities, such as games and roleplay, are designed to promote appropriate communication and develop learners (Brown 2014, Richards and Rodgers 2014). (Savignon, 2006) also argues that learners are required to negotiate meaning to achieve the desired competence. According to (Knight 2001), "*the learner can communicate successfully in the target language in real situations, rather than have a conscious understanding of the rules governing that language.*" Another distinctive feature is that it enhances learners' motivation to learn a language, and the CLT approach encourages the learning of English through the use of authentic and real-world materials

(Littlewood 1985). To practice a language effectively, different means used as teaching aids, such as communication games, problem-solving, and activity cards. (Richards and Rodgers, 2001) identified three different types of materials, including text-based materials, task-based materials, and realia. Thus, teachers offer the learners of CLT opportunities to interact and communicate genuinely, which enables them to understand a language as it used by fluent speakers (Canale and Swain, 1980). This technique contrasts with traditional language learning methods, such as GTM. Learners acquire a language by interacting with others. Hence, students should perform communicative activities in small groups to maximize their language 52 practices. However, this dimension of CLT can be challenging to implement in large classes with high numbers of students as it is challenging to meet all of the students' needs (Ju, 2013). What characterizes CLT is also its label as a learner-centered approach, which alters both the teachers' and students' roles. In CLT, the teacher-centered learning process on the learners, who *"are seen as being able to assume a more active and participatory role than is usual in traditional approaches"* (Tudor 1993:22). Students play a more responsible role during the learning process, by taking part and making sense of what they are learning. To develop and enhance this active student role, students should be given a high level of tolerance and comfort, which consequently requires teachers to change their positions and adopt more active and facilitative roles. (Ahmad and Rao, 2013) point out, *"teachers abandoned lecture notes and PowerPoint presentations for a more energetic, engaging, collaborative style of teaching"*. Thus, this kind of stimulating environment encourages students to participate freely in class without being concerned about making mistakes.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Methodology

Cox and Haddrd, 2010) define research design as clearly identified structures within which a research study implemented. This study employed a descriptive research method, which used direct explanation, analysis, and description of a particular phenomenon without the interference of the researcher (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). This method enabled the researcher to identify and describe the characteristics of the study population and their relationships. Moreover, Parahoo, (2006, p. 12) claimed that *"to achieve the objectives and aims of the study it is essential for the researcher to choose the most suitable design for achieving the objectives of the study"*. A quantitative method using a descriptive design had recommended for this study. A questionnaire had used as the data collection tool. According to (Parahoo, 2006) the quantitative method initiated from the idea that human phenomena and variables in human behavior had been studied objectively hence this method had carefully selected as a suitable research approach. (Robson, 2007) added that quantitative research uses a solid design that organizes in advance the research question and a comprehensive method for data collection and analysis.

3.2 Sample of the Study

(Proctor et al., 2010) define a sample as “a proportion of a population”. Furthermore, (Proctor et al., 2010), claims that, in quantitative research, the size of the sample should be calculated at the design stage According to (OECD, 2012) the sampling technique is the specific process through which the entities of the sample are selected. This study employed simple random sampling technique to pick the study sample. (Mugenda et al., 2012) define random sampling technique as a method that gives elements through which a study population an equally chance of being sampled. A sample size comprises a group of respondents, consisting of part of the target population carefully selected to represent that population (Cooper and Schindler (2014). For this reason, it is suggested to use a sample size of 100 English language teachers from Omdurman locality-Sudan. The participants will be selected using a simple random sampling method.

4. Results and Discussion

This section is mainly devoted to data analysis of the data collected through questionnaire. The researcher obtained (100) responses for the participants of the study. The collected data entered into (SPSS) for statistical treatment and producing the outputs in order to answer the main research question. Suitable statistical methods used to include the descriptive and inferential statistical methods.

The statistical analysis in this section will proceed to cover the assessment of the sample responses towards the questionnaire dimensions.

4.1 Results of Research Questions

This part of data analysis is devoted to answer the following research questions.

4.1.1 Discussion of research question one: What is the relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective usage of communicative approach?

To answer this question, the researcher used mean, standard deviation and chi square test for the statement on the first dimension – as shown in the following table.

Table 1: The relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective usage of communicative approach

Statements	Mean	STD	Rank	Chi-square	p-value	Level
1. I think using CLT in my classroom helps my whole teaching process.	4.56	0.74	1	105.5	0.000	Strongly Agree
2. Using CLT helps in building strong relationship between me and my students	4.41	0.74	6	70.4	0.000	Strongly Agree
3. Using CLT in my classroom helps me share ideas and, opinions with my learners	4.49	0.69	2	85.8	0.000	Strongly Agree

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4. Using CLT in my classroom helps me brainstorming ideas about different topics.	4.40	0.71	7	122.2	0.000	Strongly Agree
5. Using CLT in my classroom will help me to communicate effectively with my students inside and outside the classroom	4.45	0.73	5	124.8	0.000	Strongly Agree
6. I think using CLT in my classroom makes me more creative.	4.46	0.70	4	80.2	0.000	Strongly Agree
7. I believe using CLT is only wasting students' time.	4.48	0.84	3	144.8	0.000	Strongly Agree
Total	4.46	0.74				Strongly Agree

Table 1 shows the mean, standard deviation and non-parametric chi-square test for goodness of fit of the answers of each statement in the first dimension: The relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective usage of communicative approach.

The mean of the whole dimension which is (4.46) lies in the range (4.20 – 5.0) – according to Five-Likert scale. Moreover, the results of chi-square test show significant difference for each statement at level (0.01) which indicates that the majority of participants strongly agree to the statements of the first dimension, i.e. the majority of participants strongly agree that there is relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective usage of communicative approach – in general.

According to the mean value of each statement, the statements have been reordering in descending order from the highest mean to the lowest, so we find that the statement (1. I think using CLT in my classroom helps my whole teaching process) came in the first order with the highest mean (4.56) and level of response (Strongly Agree), then the statement (3. Using CLT in my classroom helps me share ideas and, opinions with my learners) came in the second order with mean (4.49) and level of response (Strongly Agree), then the statement (7. I believe using CLT is only wasting students' time) came in the third order with mean (4.48) and level of response (Strongly Agree), then the statement (6. I think using CLT in my classroom makes me more creative) came in the fourth order with mean (4.46) and level of response (Strongly Agree), then the statement (5. Using CLT in my classroom will help me to communicate effectively with my students inside and outside the classroom) came in the fifth order with mean (4.45) and level of response (Strongly Agree), then the statement (2. Using CLT helps in building strong relationship between me and my students) came in the sixth order with mean (4.41) and level of response (Strongly Agree), then the statement (4. Using CLT in my classroom helps me brainstorming ideas about different topics) came in the seventh order with mean (4.40) and level of response (Strongly Agree).

4.1.2 Discussion of research question two: What are the effective factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach to develop students speaking skills?

To answer this question, the researcher used mean, standard deviation and chi-square test for the statement on the second dimension – as shown in the following table.

Table 2: The effective factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach to develop students speaking skills

Statements	Mean	STD	Rank	Chi-square	p-value	Level
1. Lack of authentic materials hinder the use of CLT in my classroom.	4.39	1.02	1	132.7	0.000	Strongly agree
2. Classroom size makes using CLT in my classroom more difficult.	4.30	0.95	2	104.3	0.000	Strongly agree
3. Insufficient speaking tasks in the curriculum deprives me from using CLT in my teaching process.	3.95	1.01	6	60.7	0.000	Agree
4. Centralized grammar-based exams are at odds with the use of CLT in my class.	4.14	0.91	4	79.9	0.000	Agree
5. Developing CLT material for communicative classes needs more time.	3.98	1.05	5	66.7	0.000	Agree
6. Student' prior knowledge hinders using CLT in my classroom	3.79	1.27	7	40.5	0.000	Agree
7. Inadequate training in CLT is a key barrier of using it in my classroom	4.23	0.63	3	80.7	0.000	Strongly agree
Total	4.11	0.98				Agree

Table 2 shows the mean, standard deviation and non-parametric chi-square test for goodness of fit of the answers of each statement in the second dimension: The effective factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach to develop students speaking skills.

The mean of the whole dimension which is (4.11) lies in the range (3.40 –< 4.20) – according to Five-Likert scale. Moreover, the results of chi-square test show significant difference for each statement at level (0.01) which indicates that the majority of participants agree to the statements of the second dimension, i.e. the majority of participants agree that there are effective factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach to develop students speaking skills – in general.

According to the mean value of each statement, the statements have been reordering in descending order from the highest mean to the lowest, so we find that the statement (1. Lack of authentic materials hinder the use of CLT in my classroom) came firstly with the highest mean (4.39) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (2. Classroom size makes using CLT in my classroom more difficult) came in the second order with mean (4.30) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the

statement (7. Inadequate training in CLT is a key barrier of using it in my classroom) came in the third order with mean (4.23) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (4. Centralized grammar-based exams are at odds with the use of CLT in my class) came in the fourth order with mean (4.14) and level of response (Agree), then the statement (5. Developing CLT material for communicative classes needs more time) came in the fifth order with mean (3.98) and level of response (Agree), then the statement (3. Insufficient speaking tasks in the curriculum deprives me from using CLT in my teaching process) came in the sixth order with mean (3.95) and level of response (Agree), then the statement (6. Students' prior knowledge hinder using CLT in my classroom) came in the seventh order with mean (3.79) and level of response (Agree).

4.1.3 Discussion of research question three: To what extents does the communicative approach develop students speaking skills?

To answer this question, the researcher used mean, standard deviation and chi-square test for the statement on the third dimension – as shown in the following table.

Table 3: The communicative approach does develop students speaking skills

Statements	Mean	STD	Rank	Chi-square	p-value	Level
1. Using CLT enhances students speaking skills	4.53	0.73	1	144.8	0.000	Strongly agree
2. I think using CLA motivates my students to speak fluently inside and outside the classroom.	4.37	0.75	4	64.9	0.000	Strongly agree
3. Students' low motivation for communicative competence makes the use of CLT in my classroom a more challenging task.	4.25	0.70	6	123.5	0.000	Strongly agree
4. I think using CLT motivates my student to speak accurately inside and outside the classroom.	4.47	0.72	2	129.9	0.000	Strongly agree
5. Using CLT encourages me to spend more time on pair work rather than on grammatical rules	4.35	0.83	5	105.7	0.000	Strongly agree
6. I think using CLT allows my students to use target language in the classroom	4.43	0.62	3	92.5	0.000	Strongly agree
Total	4.40	0.73				Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows the mean, standard deviation and non-parametric chi-square test for goodness of fit of the answers of each statement in the third dimension: The communicative approach to develop students speaking skills.

The mean of the whole dimension which is (4.40) lies in the range (4.20 – 5.0) – according to Five-Likert scale. Moreover, the results of chi-square test show significant difference for each statement at level (0.01) which indicates that the majority of participants strongly agree to the statements of the third dimension, i.e. the majority of

participants strongly agree that the communicative approach do develop students speaking skills – in general.

According to the mean value of each statement, the statements have been reordering in descending order from the highest mean to the lowest, so we find that the statement (1. Using CLT enhances students speaking skills) came in the first order with the highest mean (4.53) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (4. I think using CLT motivates my student to speak accurately inside and outside the classroom) came in the second order with mean (4.47) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (6. I think using CLT allows my students to use target language in the classroom) came in the third order with mean (4.43) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (2. I think using CLT motivates my students to speak fluently inside and outside the classroom) came in the fourth order with mean (4.37) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (5. Using CLT encourages me to spend more time on pair work rather than on explicit grammatical rule) came in the fifth order with mean (4.35) and level of response (Strongly agree), then the statement (3. Students' low motivation for communicative competence makes the use of CLT in my classroom a more challenging task) came in the sixth order with mean (4.25) and level of response (Strongly agree).

5. Findings and Recommendations

This section concludes the thesis by answering the research questions proposed at the beginning of the research. Then the findings discussion is presented and followed by proposed recommendation that will provide great input regarding university students' motivation and English language learning. At the end of this section, conclusion is drawn from this study. Also, this section provides a suggestion for further studies.

5.1 Findings

- 1) The majority of participants strongly agree that there is a positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective usage of the communicative approach. The mains statements that gathered the highest level of response are: I think using CLA in my classroom helps my whole teaching process and using CLA in my class helps me share ideas and opinions with my learners. This means that most of the study participants assured that the use of CLT in the classrooms helped them to share the knowledge and facilitated their teaching process.
- 2) The majority of participants agree that there are effective factors that hinder teachers from using communicative approach to develop students speaking skills. The main statements which gathered their highest level of response are the following: Lack of authentic materials hinder the use of CLA in my and Classroom size makes using CLA in my classroom more difficult. This clearly shows that the most effective factors that hinder teachers from implementing CLT in their classes are lacking of authentic material and classroom size

- 3) The majority of participants strongly agree that the communicative approach to develop students speaking skills – in general, and the main statements which gathered their highest level of response: Using CLA enhances students speaking skills, and I think using CLA motivates my student to speak accurately inside and outside the classroom. This result indicates that their participants of the study confirmed that using CLT in classroom enhanced their students speaking skill and motivated them to speak fluently.

5.2 Pedagogical Implications and Recommendations

Teachers have to consider many pedagogical implications when it comes to implementing CLT activities in the classroom. Most of the Sudanese secondary school teachers still think the traditional way of teaching and book-based teaching to be the most suitable method when it comes to teaching EFL students. Nevertheless, it is essential to consider other approaches to teaching to differentiate the teaching technique in the classroom.

Therefore, the researcher suggested the following recommendations:

- 1) Teachers are encouraged to attempt to implement CLT activities in the classroom to find out whether learners prefer this type of instruction or not.
- 2) Secondary school teachers have to carry out a needs analysis to determine what type of communicative activities students feel is relatable and comfortable to participate in their classes.
- 3) The administration of educational institutions is required to provide teachers with authentic materials to be able to implement CLT effectively in the classroom.

5.3 Suggestions for Future Studies

The application of the CLT approach should be tested on different levels of education, such as primary, elementary, secondary and higher education. All the four language skills should be included in language assessment. Further work is also needed in syllabus design for the CLT approach. Moreover, future study should be conducted on the effectiveness of modern Technology on implementing CLT activities in Sudanese secondary schools setting.

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